

Entropy as Average Information Versus Information in Constraints

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In (1), generalized entropy is written as : $\sum_i p(i) h(p(i))$. In other words, if $h(p(i))$ is information, then entropy is the average value of this information using $p(i)$ to calculate the average. (1) considers maximizing this entropy subject to the constraints $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$ and $\sum_i p(i) = 1$. The question we ask is: What is the information contained in the above entropy that exists outside of the constraints? The constraints certainly represent information and one may consider, as an example, that they contain all of the information in the system. In such a case, entropy does not contain any more information than the constraints. Given that $\sum_i p(i)=1$ is a general constraint, the key information is then $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$ (or some other expression). In other words, in such a case entropy mimics the second constraint condition and is not an independent function, i.e. $h(p(i)) = -e_i/T$.

In the case that entropy represents only the information contained in the constraints, then the differentials of the constraints must be equivalent to the differential of entropy. (1) argues that one may write in general: $d/dp \{ p h(p) \} + a + b e_i/T = 0$ and considers the cases of the Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis entropies. We argue that the above maximization only holds for the Shannon case. In the Tsallis case, the correct second constraint is: $\sum_i e_i p(i)^q$ and in the Kaniadakis case, even though the second constraint is $\sum_i e_i p(i)$, it is the Shannon entropy and not the Kaniadakis one which satisfies the maximization equation suggesting that the Kaniadakis entropy contains more information than the Shannon one.

Entropy As Average Information

In (1), it is proposed that one write a generalized entropy as:

$$\sum_i p(i) h(p(i)) \quad ((1))$$

This is of the form of an average equation, if $p(i)$ is used to calculate the average. Hence $h(p(i))$ must represent the function being averaged, i.e some information about the system.

Furthermore, one states a priori that there are two pieces of information known about the system (according to (1)):

$$\sum_i p(i) = 1 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave} \quad ((2b))$$

The question then becomes: Is it possible that these two constraints represent all of the information in a system? It is possible that in this in this case, entropy contains no more information than what is in these constraints? Then, given that ((2a)) is general, ((1)) should mimic the second constraint, i.e:

$$h(p(i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((3))$$

Thus, entropy is not really independent of the second constraint in such a scenario. Taking the differential of ((1)) should yield an expression equivalent to a linear combination of the differentials of the constraints ((2a)), ((2b)). Thus:

$$h(p(i)) + p(i) dh/dp(i) \text{ is compared with } a \text{ (ei) and } b \text{ ((4))}$$

$$\text{Then: } a = -1/T \text{ and if } b=1, p dh/dp = 1 \text{ or } h = \ln(p) \text{ ((5))}$$

((5)) is the Shannon case. Using the constraints ((2a)), ((2b)), the Shannon entropy represents a system whose complete information is contained by ((2a)), ((2b)), i.e. the constraints. There is no further information.

The question then becomes: What happens in the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases. In (1) is argued that one may write:

$$h(p) + p dh/dp + a + b \sum e_i = 0 \text{ ((6))}$$

This is the maximization of the generalized average form entropy subject to the constraints ((2a)) and ((2b)). One basically states that the differential of the entropy function is equivalent to a linear combination of the differentials of the two constraints ((2a)) and ((2b)). This implies that there is no extra information in $\sum p(i) h(p(i))$ and that it should mimic the second constraint ((2b)). This means that ((6)) holds for Shannon's entropy and not for the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases.

This may be tested explicitly. Using $h(p) = 1/(1-q) \{ 1 + (1-q) p^{1-q} \}$ ((7)) as given in (1), one has:

$$-e_i/T + e_i/T + a + (1-q) p^{1-q} \neq 0 \text{ for } b=1/T \text{ ((7))}$$

In order to deal with Tsallis entropy one may replace the constraint ((2b)) with $\sum p(i)^q e_i = F$ and then argue that ((2a)) and this new constraint contain all of the information contained in the system. Then:

$$h(p) + q p^{q-1} + p^q dh/dp + a + p^q e_i/T = 0 \text{ ((8))}$$

$$\text{If } a = 1-q \text{ ((9))}$$

In the Kaniadakis case, using ((6)) and: $h(p) = 1/2k (p^k - p^{-k})$ and $p = (\sqrt{1+kx} + kx)^{1/k}$ where $x = -e_i/T$, both expressions given in (1), one finds that:

$$-e/T + a + e/T + \sqrt{1+kx} \neq 0 \text{ ((10))}$$

((10)) is 0 for $k=0$ and almost 0 for $x \ll 1$ ((11)).

Thus, the Kaniadakis entropy does not maximize entropy subject to the constraints ((2a)) and ((2b)) which is fine because it is Shannon's entropy which maximizes entropy under these conditions.

Thus, we argue that one must be careful about what maximization of entropy subject to constraints means. Using the form $\sum_i p(i) h(p(i))$ means that entropy represents the average of the function $h(p(i))$, but the differential of this is compared to the differential of two constraints, $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$ and $\sum_i p(i) = 1$. If $h(p(i)) = -e_i/T$, then one is mathematically describing a system whose information is only that of the constraints and not more. (In the Tsallis case, ((2b)) is replaced with the constraint $\sum_i p(i)^q = 1$.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, if one decides to write entropy as $\sum_i p(i) h(p(i))$, then it is explicitly in the form of an average expression using $p(i)$, where $h(p(i))$ is being averaged. If one uses the constraints $\sum_i p(i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$, then these represent information. The question is whether $\sum_i p(i) h(p(i))$ represents more information. If $h(p(i))$ is to be equal to $-e_i/T$, then entropy does not represent more information and essentially mimics the second constraint $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$. This is the Shannon case. The Tsallis case uses $\sum_i p(i)^q = 1$ as the constraint and then entropy simply mimics this. In the Kaniadakis case, $\sum_i e_i p(i) = E_{ave}$ is the constraint, so using Entropy = $\sum_i p(i) h(p(i))$, with $h(p(i)) = -e_i/T$ means that this expression does not maximize entropy subject to the constraints, because Shannon's entropy does in this case.

References

1. Beck, C. Generalized Information and Entropy in Physics (2009)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/0902.1235>